

**A STUDY TO EXAMINE THE INTRA
RELIABILITY OF RAPID UPPER LIMB
ASSESSMENT (RULA) IN COMPUTER
OPERATORS**

INTRODUCTION

1.1. INTRODUCTION

The International Labour Organization (ILO) and the World Health Organization (WHO) regard musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) as a work-related disease, which is also referred to as a “new epidemic” that should be researched and solved.¹ MSDs have a huge impact on work-related absence and a high proportion of days lost is due to MSDs.² Therefore, it not only affects the health of workers but also creates a burden on the health system, on the businesses economic, and on the social costs to deal with their consequences.¹ MSDs prophylaxis is needed in many countries to allow workers to avoid the symptoms of MSDs, improve working productivity, and reduce the burden on medical systems at the same time.³ In developing countries like India, many programs for the prevention of MSDs have been applied on workplace.

The work-related musculoskeletal disorder is estimated to affect 4% of the total world population with addition of 160 million new cases of work-related disorder per year,⁴ according to the International Labour Office (ILO). Among them 15% of cases are from work-place factors particular to the biomechanical factors.⁵ Overall this leads to reduction in production, absenteeism and early retirement.² Well-being is defined as not only the absence of disease and reduced physical functioning, but the presence of positive physical, mental, and psychosocial states of being. Computers have become an integral part of offices and work places. However, there is also an increasing prevalence of upper quadrant symptoms with computer usage. Neck and shoulder are the most susceptible areas for developing musculoskeletal symptoms among computer users. The modifiable risk factors for these work related musculoskeletal disorders include physical office environment and psychosocial work related factors. Computer workstation layout had been shown to be an

important physical aspect of work environment that influences the upper quadrant symptoms.⁶ Ergonomics is a relatively new concept in India yet to be considered an essential component of most enterprises.⁷ The nature of ergonomics performs a unique role in protecting human health and preventing health risks.⁸ Introduction of adjustable workstations is an important step in application of ergonomics. A focus on following ergonomic principals can lead to a reduction in musculoskeletal problems and increase in productivity of the workers.⁹ The relevance of this science to design a workplace in terms of tasks of the employee, making use of tools and the environment is called ergonomic design. A good ergonomic design not only maximizes the capabilities of workers by increasing efficiency and job satisfaction, but also gives a payback to the company by decreasing the cost for health and absence of workers due to health conditions. In further terminology, ergonomics makes sure “appropriating the duty to the worker”

During the 21th century, the banking sector in India is witnessing a tremendous change because of globalization, liberalization and other worldwide proceedings. It has been reported that there is an increased chance of developing upper limb symptoms due to the risk factors at workplace.⁷ Considerable changes have affected both directly and indirectly. These are common, monetary and psychosomatic subject of bank employees and India. These are the potential causes of occupational stress and related disorders among employees in the banking sector of India. Conventional wisdom suggests that due to internal and external changes, employees in the banking sector in India are facing high levels of stress. Extended Perceived stress in Indiai bankers is causing them to suffer from exhaustion. A flexible work environment would have a positive influence on the productivity of the individuals. Neck and shoulder pain have been found to be associated with

prolonged working hours and improper sitting postures.¹⁰ Sustained sitting postures and poor workstation designs have been found to be linked with development of musculoskeletal disorders among computer users.¹⁰ Bankers have to work for prolonged durations on computer workstations and may have to work overtime as well.

RULA (rapid upper limb assessment) is a survey method developed for use in ergonomics investigations of workplaces where work-related upper limb disorders are reported. This tool requires no special equipment in providing a quick assessment of the postures of the neck, trunk and upper limbs along with muscle function and the external loads experienced by the body. A coding system is used to generate an action list which indicates the level of intervention required to reduce the risks of injury due to physical loading on the operator.¹¹ RULA is a subjective observation method of posture analysis that focuses on the upper body, but includes the lower body. It requires no previous skills in observation techniques and is easy to learn. RULA has previously been shown to be reliable with adults.¹¹ Statistical calculations were not published but the authors state that the scores indicated a high consistency among assessors.¹¹ RULA is found to be valid and reliable for the rapid assessment of computer workers.¹² Maintaining ideal body posture is essential for the prevention of MSD among this large population. This study aimed to examine the validity and reliability of RULA among the bank employees' using computers.

1.2. Need for the study

Although Rapid upper limb assessment methodology was derived from principles related to physiology, biomechanics, and epidemiology of upper extremity and cervical disorders, no studies exist which proves the test-retest capability of RULA. Reliability of a tool is the capability of the instrument to replicate previous measurements of the same object of study.¹³ This is usually broken into intra- and inter-rater reliability. Intra-rater reliability is the ability of a tool to reproduce measurements independent of the time when measurements are recorded.^{13,14} Intra-rater reliability is also known as test stability or test-retest repeatability; the latter synonym will be used in this study. The purpose of this study is to investigate intra-rater reliability of the Rapid upper limb assessment tool.

1.3. Objective of the study:

To estimate validity and reliability of RULA among the employee operating computers working in bank

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Namwongsa et al (2018) used RULA in assessing ergonomic risk assessment among the smartphone users. The number of smartphone users globally is rapidly increasing. Their study aimed to assess the level of ergonomic risk to smartphone users, and to evaluate the correlation between any self-reported musculoskeletal disorders and the level of ergonomic risk. Thirty participants completed a questionnaire, tailored specifically for smartphone users, to determine any musculoskeletal disorders. Participants were given a seated smartphone texting task and their postures were video recorded during the task. The video scenarios were evaluated by three independent researchers to determine the level of ergonomic risk using the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) tool. RULA is an observation-based screening tool which has been widely used to assess the postural risk of IT device users. However, it has not yet been specifically utilized with smartphone users. The RULA tool scores identified ergonomics risks from using smartphones to text. Most smartphone users had a total RULA Grand Score of 6 for both sides (left side: 80.00%, right side: 90.00%), indicating the need for further investigation and changes (Action Level 3). Notably, no participants had acceptable RULA Grand Scores of 1 or 2. The correlation between musculoskeletal disorders and the ergonomic risk among smartphone users was determined using the Chi-Square test and Fisher's exact test; $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. There was a significant correlation between right RULA Grand Score and neck musculoskeletal disorder ($\chi^2 = 9.424$ at p value = 0.009) and right RULA Grand Score and upper back musculoskeletal disorder ($\chi^2 = 31.717$ at p value < 0.001). RULA Score B (combination of neck, trunk and leg postures) and RULA Score D (combination of Score B, muscle use and force scores for group B) were also

significantly correlated with neck musculoskeletal disorders ($\chi^2 = 19.286$ at p value < 0.001 and $\chi^2 = 9.310$ at p value = 0.002 respectively). The RULA results identified the high ergonomics risk of smartphone users, this resulted from two key risk factors: posture and muscle use. The neck, trunk and leg postures had a combined effect on neck musculoskeletal disorders. Future investigations should consider these factors when designing ergonomic interventions for smartphone users.¹⁵

Sellschop et al (2018) studied the ergonomic behaviour of learners in a digitally driven school environment.¹⁶ They argued that the computer use is increasing amongst adolescents and so is the potential for related musculoskeletal pain and postural changes. The cumulative effect of this technology-induced, sedentary lifestyle leads to poor posture, pain, repetitive strain injury and dysfunctional movement patterns. The purpose of their study was to establish the effect of a computer-related ergonomic intervention for adolescents in a school environment on posture and ergonomic behaviour. They took all Grade 8 learners at two randomly selected private schools in Johannesburg were invited to participate in the study ($n = 127$). A controlled trial compared an intervention group with a control group. The computer usage questionnaire and rapid upper limb assessment (RULA) were assessed at baseline, 3 and 6 months post-intervention. The intervention consisted of a participatory educational programme. An intention-to-treat analysis was undertaken. Alpha level was set at $p = 0.05$. Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) and between-group analysis of variance, determined differences in the number of participants in the RULA action levels between groups after the intervention and the comparison of positions and type of computer.¹⁶ At 6 months post-intervention, there were no participants in action level (AL) 4 and the number of

participants in AL 3 had reduced from 26.2% at baseline to 14.8% in the intervention group ($p < 0.001$). The control group RULA scores worsened over the period of 6 months. Although the learners were still not in an 'acceptable' range of postural positions, there was a significant improvement between the pre-intervention and post-intervention stage ($p < 0.001$). Their findings demonstrate the effect of an ergonomic intervention and its sustainability over 6 months. The clinical contribution of their study to our healthcare system is that through the early identification and intervention of the poor ergonomics in a school environment, a positive impact on reducing.¹⁶

Valentim et al (2018) reported the reliability, construct validity and interpretability of the Brazilian version of RULA and Strain Index (SI).¹⁷ There are very few observational methods for analysis of biomechanical exposure available in Brazilian-Portuguese. Their study aimed to cross-culturally adapt and test the measurement properties of RULA and Strain Index (SI). They performed the cross-cultural adaptation and measurement properties test as established according to Beaton et al. and COSMIN guidelines, respectively. Several tasks that required static posture and/or repetitive motion of upper limbs were evaluated ($n > 100$). Finally, they have reported the intra-raters' reliability for the RULA ranged from poor to almost perfect (k : 0.00-0.93), and SI from poor to excellent (ICC2.1: 0.05-0.99). The inter-raters' reliability was very poor for RULA (k : -0.12 to 0.13) and ranged from very poor to moderate for SI (ICC2.1: 0.00-0.53). The agreement was good for RULA (75-100% intra-raters, and 42.24-100% inter-raters) and to SI (EPM: -1.03% to 1.97%; intra-raters, and -0.17% to 1.51% inter-raters).¹⁷ The internal consistency was appropriate for RULA ($\alpha=0.88$), and low for SI ($\alpha=0.65$). Moderate construct validity were observed between RULA and SI, in wrist/hand-wrist posture (ρ : 0.61) and

strength/intensity of exertion (ρ : 0.39). Hence, they have concluded that the adapted versions of the RULA and SI presented semantic and cultural equivalence for the Brazilian Portuguese.¹⁷ The RULA and SI had reliability estimates ranged from very poor to almost perfect. The internal consistency for RULA was better than the SI. The correlation between methods was moderate only of muscle request/movement repetition. Previous training is mandatory to use of observations methods for biomechanical exposure assessment, although it does not guarantee good reproducibility of these measures.¹⁷

Levanon et al (2014) established the validity of RULA among the computer workers.¹² According to them, the awkward body posture while typing is associated with musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs). Valid rapid assessment of computer workers' body posture is essential for the prevention of MSD among this large population. Their study aimed to examine the validity of the modified rapid upper limb assessment (mRULA) which adjusted the rapid upper limb assessment (RULA) for computer workers. Their study examined whether one observation during a working day is sufficient or more observations are needed. A total of 29 right-handed computer workers were recruited. RULA and mRULA were conducted. The observations were then repeated six times at one-hour intervals. A significant moderate correlation ($r = 0.6$ and $r = 0.7$ for mouse and keyboard, respectively) was found between the assessments. No significant differences were found between one observation and six observations per working day. The mRULA was found to be valid for the assessment of computer workers, and one observation was sufficient to assess the work-related risk factor.¹²

Dockrell et al (2012) investigated the reliability of RULA as a method of assessment of children's computing posture.¹⁸ They confirmed that RULA is a quick observation

method of posture analysis. RULA has been used to assess children's computer-related posture, but the reliability of RULA on a paediatric population has not been established. The purpose of their study was to investigate the inter-rater and intra-rater reliability of the use of RULA with children. Video recordings of 24 school children were independently viewed by six trained raters who assessed their postures using RULA, on two separate occasions. RULA demonstrated higher intra-rater reliability than inter-rater reliability although both were moderate to good. RULA was more reliable when used for assessing the older children (8-12 years) than with the younger children (4-7 years). RULA may prove useful as part of an ergonomic assessment, but its level of reliability warrants caution for its sole use when assessing children, and in particular, younger children.¹⁸

Bao S et al. (2007) This paper presents two posture risk quantification methods: first, an event-based method where the most common and the worst postures are estimated in a task; second, a time-based method where posture distributions are calculated from random samples of observed postures in the task.¹⁹ A 'click-on-screen' posture data entry method was developed for the time-based posture analysis method to make the observation process easier and to reduce possible posture categorization bias. Both methods were used to quantify various work posture parameters among a study cohort of 733 subjects from a prospective epidemiological study of upper extremity musculoskeletal disorders. Composite posture indices using a modified Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) method were also computed using data obtained by the two posture analysis methods. Results showed that both methods were able to distinguish jobs with large differences in certain posture measures.¹⁹

Gandavadi et al (2007) Conducted a study on 60 dental students' posture on two different seats in order to determine if one seat predisposes to a difference in working posture.²⁰ RULA was able to identify that Bambach saddle seats were better than conventional seats. The study was undertaken at the University of Birmingham School of Dentistry in 2006.²⁰ Sixty second year dental students at the University of Birmingham who were attending their first classes in the phantom head laboratory were randomly selected and allocated to two different seats (30 Bambach Saddle Seats and 30 conventional seats). Students were trained in the use of the seats. After ten weeks, the students were observed, photographs were taken by the researcher and these were assessed using RULA.²⁰

Breen et al (2007) This study investigated schoolchildren's posture and discomfort while working at computers.²¹ Sixty-eight children (mean age 9.5 years) were observed at school during normal computer sessions lasting 15-25 min. Rapid upper limb assessment (RULA) was used to evaluate posture, and a body discomfort chart (BDC) and a modified visual analogue scale (VAS) were used to record site and intensity of discomfort.²¹ Computer tasks were noted and in accordance with RULA, postures were classified as Action Level (AL) 1 (acceptable) to 4 (needs immediate change). Most children adopted postures at an unacceptable level while working at computers. None of the postures were in AL 1; 60% were in AL 2; 38% were in AL 3; and 2% were in AL 4. Posture became worse over time. Poor posture was associated with discomfort, but it is not clear if it was related to the sitting posture or to the computer use. Children who reported discomfort had a higher mean RULA grand score (5.0) than those who did not report discomfort (4.4). The type of computer task influenced the children's posture. RULA proved generally to be a suitable method for evaluating children's posture.²¹

Massaccesi et al (2003) RULA proved to be a suitable tool for rapid evaluation of loading of neck and trunk in professional truck drivers.²² A sample of 77 drivers, of rubbish-collection vehicles who sit in a standard posture and of road-washing vehicles, who drive with the neck and trunk flexed, bent and twisted, was studied using RULA, a method for the evaluation of the exposure to risk factors associated with work-related upper-limb disorders. Two sets of truck drivers were compared one who sits in standard posture compare with one who sits with stooped posture. There were a significant association between RULA trunk and neck score and all self-reported pain ache and discomfort. RULA neck scores were statistically more significant reflecting high loading of the neck. The study displayed that loading of the spine can be assessed using RULA.²² A high incidence of spinal disorders is observed in professional drivers; in particular, back and neck pain result in high rates of morbidity and low retirement age. In particular, the neck score was significant in both postures, reflecting high loading of the neck. Significantly different posture scores were also recorded for drivers using an adjustable and a non-adjustable seat.²²

Fountain LJ (2000) conducted a study on 20 subjects to compare and examine physiological and psychological parameters in the working population.²³ The variables used in this study were surface electromyography, rapid upper limb assessment, self-reports of discomfort and job attitude. A thirty minute typing task in three different postures was used. There was no change in any of the variables except for perceived discomfort. The study also demonstrated that RULA was able to distinguish "high risk" patient.²³

McAtamney et al (1993) RULA was devised by McAtamney L and Nigel Corlett E to aid in ergonomic investigations of workplaces where work-related upper limb

disorders are reported.¹¹ It also fulfills the assessment requirements of both the European Community Directive (90/270/EEC) on the minimum safety and health requirements for work with display screen equipment and the UK Guidelines on the prevention of work-related upper limb disorders. This tool requires no special equipment in providing a quick assessment of the postures of the neck, trunk and upper limbs along with muscle function and the external loads experienced by the body. A coding system is used to generate an action list which indicates the level of intervention required to reduce the risks of injury due to physical loading on the operator.¹¹

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study design

- The study design will be a cross-Sectional Study, correlation study

3.2 Ethical Clearance

- Ethical clearance from Institutional Ethical committee of Srinivas university, Mangaluru, Karnataka reference number SRNU/2008/936 dated 24.06.2008

3.3 Study location

- Bank employees will be recruited from the State bank of India (SBI) and associated banks in Mangalore

3.4 Study settings

- The study will be conducted at the office premises of bank employees

3.5 Study population

- The study will be performed on primary school going children

3.6 Sampling

- Simple random sampling (computer generated random numbers)

3.7 Subject selection criteria

3.7.1 Inclusion criteria

- 25 -40 years of age, (before menopause in female).
- Male and female with normal development
- Working in computers

3.7.2 Exclusion criteria

- Impaired Vision (initially asked about the vision problem or medically pre-diagnosed child)
- Low back pain
- Any other medical, surgical and psychological conditions that prevent the child participation

3.8 Sample size

Total 300 bank employee will be recruited for the study.

3.9 Study duration

The data collection was done from August- 2017 to March- 2018)

3.10 Outcome measures

- RULA (Figure 4.5.1)
- REBA (Figure 4.5.2)

3.11 Materials used for data collection

- Video camera Canon 720
- Measuring tape,(Cobra[®], 60 inches, 152 cm)
- Weighing machine (Krupps[®])
- Computer
- Computer software – Ergonomics posture analysis tool
- RULA forms and manuals

3.12. DETAILED PROCEDURE OF PRESENT WORK

Ten physiotherapists will be asked to rate digitized video files (AVI files) chosen by the researcher to be representative of the computer industry as well as covering the full range of the RULA task variables. Once the task variables were assigned a rating, the ratings will be used to calculate a final RULA score.

The rater cohort will consist of ten physiotherapists. All participants, regardless of experience, will be given an eight-hour tutorial on using the Rapid upper limb assessment. This included background on RULA principles, RULA applications, video files examples of jobs, demonstrations on how to apply ratings to video files, and an open discussion of example results. Each rater will be given a DVD containing 75 job video files, an instruction and procedure manual. Each participant will be asked to evaluate job video files as directed by the instruction manual and to use the enclosed forms to record task variable ratings, estimates, observations, and/or calculations. The participants will be asked to mail the forms to the researchers. The second round started between three and seven months after conclusion of round one. In round two, participants will be requested to individually re-evaluate the same video files, repeating the process from the initial evaluation.

Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA.) scores will be calculated for the posture of each body part. A score of 1 indicates the best or most neutral posture, e.g., arms by the sides, elbows in approximately 90° flexion, wrists in neutral position, forearms mid-way between pronation and supination, neck in 10° flexion, trunk and legs sitting and well supported. A score of 4 indicates the worst position: e.g., shoulder flexion above 90° or flexion between 45° and 90° and abduction. The combined individual scores for shoulder, elbow and wrist gave score A and those for neck, trunk and legs

gave score B. Muscle use and force exerted in each task in the video were attributed a score of 1 and 0, respectively, because they are static postures without loading; these scores will be added to scores A and B to obtain scores C and D, respectively.¹¹ Based on the design of the RULA method, each combination of scores C and D (a number of 1-7), called grand score and reflects the musculoskeletal loading associated with the worker's posture. Whereas low grand scores (of 1 or 2) indicate that the work posture is acceptable, action is suggested for the higher scores: further investigation and changes if required, for grand scores of 3 or 4; prompt investigation and changes for grand scores of 5 or 6 and immediate investigations and changes for a grand score of 7.

3.15. PROCEDURE

3.15.1. Ethical statement:

The Study protocol was approved from Institutional Ethical committee of Srinivas university, Mangaluru, Karnataka reference number SRNU/2008/936 dated 24.06.2008 in correspondence with the guidelines assigned by ICMR 2017²⁴ and ground rules framed by Declaration of Helsinki (revised 2013)²⁵.

3.15.2. Recruitment of participants:

A sample of 300 participants will take part in this study after obtaining the prior permission from the bank authorities. Written informed consent will be obtained from all the participants before their enrolment in this study. All anthropometric measurement will be taken before the beginning of the study which includes age, height and weight.

3.15.3. Validity:

The concurrent validity of RULA will be established with the criterion referenced, Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA). REBA was designed for easy use without need for an advanced degree in ergonomics or expensive equipment. Using the REBA worksheet, the evaluator will be assigned a score for each of the following body regions: wrists, forearms, elbows, shoulders, neck, trunk, back, legs and knees. After the data for each region is collected and scored, tables on the form are then will be used to compile the risk factor variables, generating a single score that represents the level of MSD risk

3.15.4. Rater training and testing:

Raters will attend a 45-min training session on the use of RULA. The session will include a lecture/demonstration using a PowerPoint presentation to introduce RULA and detailing the allocation of the scores. This will be followed by a practical session where raters could observe and evaluate four video clips of bank employee working on computers on a training DVD. Results will be compared and discussed until the raters would feel comfortable with RULA. Interpretations of the allocation of RULA scores were clarified. Following the training, raters will be allocated an individual time for their testing session. Raters will be randomly assigned DVD 1 or 2 depending on the order they will walk into the room for the training session. A set of simple instructions will be given to each participant before they start the testing session and the same procedure and protocol will be adhered for all raters. All testing will take place under similar conditions with raters seated at a desk 3 m from a screen onto which the video clips will be projected. Raters will be asked to assess the right hand side posture of each bank employee. Each rater will be allowed to take as much time as they required after each video clip to complete the RULA scoring sheet. A break will be offered to participants after every eight video clips to prevent fatigue, as established during the pilot stage of the project. The testing protocol will be repeated one week later. Each rater will view the video clips on a different randomly selected DVD than that will be viewed during the earlier session. Rater bias will be minimised by separating the two sessions by one week, by using a different DVD for each rater in session 1 and session 2 and by the fact that the raters will be requested to complete the RULA assessment sheet, but the researchers will calculate the scores at a later stage. On completion of testing the Grand Scores and the Action Levels will be calculated and cross checked by two different researchers.¹⁸

3.15.5. Reliability:

Intra-rater reliability: Intra-rater reliability of RULA will be established by the principal investigator across two trials on the same group of participants in the same environmental condition and same timings i.e. between 10:30a.m. - 11:00 a.m. in the morning with a gap of 2 days.

3.15.6. Inter- rater reliability: Inter-rater reliability of RULA will be established by the principal investigator and one other researcher (physiotherapist with five years of clinical experience) on the same group of participants with in the same environmental conditions and same timings i.e. between 10:30a.m. - 11:00 a.m in the morning with a gap of 2 minutes. Two experienced raters will analyze independently three hundred video-tasks in a randomized order. Both the raters will receive training together. After training the raters will receive 300 video-tasks to analysis (test) and reanalysis (retest) in separate. Playback of the videos could be done as often as needed and they could use a stopwatch and calculator.¹⁷

DATA ANALYSIS

3.16. Data analysis

The normality of collected data will be established by Kolmogorov-Smirnov test ($n > 50$). If the data follow normal distribution, then the descriptive statistics of demographic characteristics will be expressed in mean $\pm$ standard deviation (SD). But, If the data does not follow normal distribution, then the descriptive statistics of demographic characteristics will be expressed in mean with 95% CI, median and range. The Reliability will be established by using intra-class correlation coefficient ICC $(3, \kappa)$ for inter-rater reliability and ICC $(2, 1)$ for intra-rater reliability with 95% confidence interval (CI). According to Shrout and Fleiss (1979) ICC interpretation < 0.5 denotes poor reliability, $0.5-0.75$ to be moderate reliability, $0.75-0.90$ shows good reliability and > 0.90 as excellent reliability.²⁶ The concurrent validity of RULA will be established with the criterion measure, REBA test by spearman's rank correlation coefficient test ($n = 301$). For all data analysis level of significance (LOS) will be set as $p < 0.05$. Statistical analysis of collected data will be performed using the statistical package of social sciences (SPSS, version 20.0 Inc, Chicago, IL)

RULA Employee Assessment Worksheet

based on RULA: a survey method for the investigation of work-related upper limb disorders, McAtamney & Corlett, Applied Ergonomics 1993, 24(2), 91-99

A. Arm and Wrist Analysis

Step 1: Locate Upper Arm Position:

Step 1a: Adjust...
 If shoulder is raised: +1
 If upper arm is abducted: +1
 If arm is supported or person is leaning: -1

Step 2: Locate Lower Arm Position:

Step 2a: Adjust...
 If either arm is working across midline or out to side of body: Add +1

Step 3: Locate Wrist Position:

Step 3a: Adjust...
 If wrist is bent from midline: Add +1

Step 4: Wrist Twist:

Step 5: Look-up Posture Score in Table A:
 Using values from steps 1-4 above, locate score in Table A.

Step 6: Add Muscle Use Score
 If posture mainly static (i.e. held-10 minutes),
 Or if action repeated occurs 4X per minute: +1

Step 7: Add Force/Load Score
 If load < 4.4 lbs (intermittent): +0
 If load 4.4 to 22 lbs (intermittent): +1
 If load 4.4 to 22 lbs (static or repeated): +2
 If more than 22 lbs or repeated or shocks: +3

Step 8: Find Row in Table C
 Add values from steps 5-7 to obtain Wrist and Arm Score. Find row in Table C.

SCORES

Table A: Wrist Posture Score

Upper Arm	Lower Arm	Wrist Posture						
		1	2	3	4			
1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3
	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	3
	3	2	3	3	3	3	4	4
2	1	2	3	3	3	3	4	4
	2	3	3	3	3	4	4	4
	3	3	4	4	4	4	5	5
3	1	3	3	4	4	4	5	5
	2	3	4	4	4	4	5	5
	3	4	4	4	4	4	5	5
4	1	4	4	4	4	4	5	5
	2	4	4	4	4	4	5	5
	3	4	4	4	5	5	6	6
5	1	5	5	5	5	6	6	7
	2	5	5	6	6	6	7	7
	3	6	6	6	7	7	7	8
6	1	7	7	7	7	7	8	8
	2	8	8	8	8	8	9	9
	3	9	9	9	9	9	9	9

Table B: Trunk Posture Score

Neck	Trunk Posture					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Posture Score	1	2	1	2	1	2
	1	2	1	2	1	2
1	1	3	3	3	4	5
2	2	3	3	3	4	5
3	3	3	3	4	5	6
4	4	5	5	6	7	7
5	7	7	7	7	8	8
6	8	8	8	8	8	8

Table C: Neck, trunk and leg score

Wrist and Arm Score	Neck, trunk and leg score						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7+
1	1	2	3	3	4	5	5
2	2	2	3	4	4	5	5
3	3	3	3	4	4	5	6
4	3	3	3	4	5	6	6
5	4	4	4	5	6	7	7
6	4	4	5	6	6	7	7
7	5	5	6	6	7	7	7
8+	5	5	6	7	7	7	7

Scoring: (final score from Table C)
 1 or 2 = acceptable posture
 3 or 4 = further investigation, change may be needed
 5 or 6 = further investigation, change soon
 7 = investigate and implement change

B. Neck, Trunk and Leg Analysis

Step 9: Locate Neck Position:

Step 9a: Adjust...
 If neck is twisted: +1
 If neck is side bending: +1

Step 10: Locate Trunk Position:

Step 10a: Adjust...
 If trunk is twisted: +1
 If trunk is side bending: +1

Step 11: Legs:
 If legs and feet are supported: +1
 If not: +2

Step 12: Look-up Posture Score in Table B:
 Using values from steps 9-11 above, locate score in Table B.

Step 13: Add Muscle Use Score
 If posture mainly static (i.e. held-10 minutes),
 Or if action repeated occurs 4X per minute: +1

Step 14: Add Force/Load Score
 If load < 4.4 lbs (intermittent): +0
 If load 4.4 to 22 lbs (intermittent): +1
 If load 4.4 to 22 lbs (static or repeated): +2
 If more than 22 lbs or repeated or shocks: +3

Step 15: Find Column in Table C
 Add values from steps 12-14 to obtain Neck, Trunk and Leg Score. Find Column in Table C.

Task name: _____ Reviewer: _____ Date: ____/____/____ provided by Practical Ergonomics
 This tool is provided without warranty. The author has provided this tool as a simple means for applying the concepts provided in RULA. © 2004 Nease Consulting, Inc. rbarker@ergosmart.com (816) 444-1667

Figure 4.5.1: Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) employee assessment worksheet

REBA Employee Assessment Worksheet

Based on Technical note: Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA), Hignett, McAtamney, Applied Ergonomics 31 (2000) 201-205

A. Neck, Trunk and Leg Analysis

Step 1: Locate Neck Position

Step 1a: Adjust...
If neck is twisted: +1
If neck is side bending: +1

Step 2: Locate Trunk Position

Step 2a: Adjust...
If trunk is twisted: +1
If trunk is side bending: +3

Step 3: Legs

Step 3a: Adjust...
If leg is twisted: +1
If leg is side bending: +1

Step 4: Look-up Posture Score in Table A
Using values from steps 1-3 above, locate score in Table A.

Step 5: Add Force/Load Score
If load < 11 lbs: -0
If load 11 to 22 lbs: +1
If load > 22 lbs: +2
Adjust: If shock or rapid build up of force: add +1

Step 6: Score A, Find Row in Table C
Add values from steps 4 & 5 to obtain Score A. Find Row in Table C.

Scoring:
1 = negligible risk
2 or 3 = low risk, change may be needed
4 to 7 = medium risk, further investigation, change soon
8 to 10 = high risk, investigate and implement change
11+ = very high risk, implement change

B. Arm and Wrist Analysis

Step 7: Locate Upper Arm Position:

Step 7a: Adjust...
If shoulder is raised: +1
If upper arm is abducted: +1
If arm is supported or person is leaning: -1

Step 8: Locate Lower Arm Position:

Step 9: Locate Wrist Position:

Step 9a: Adjust...
If wrist is bent from midline or twisted: Add +1

Step 10: Look-up Posture Score in Table B
Using values from steps 7-9 above, locate score in Table B

Step 11: Add Coupling Score
Well fitting Handle and mid range power grip: good: +0
Acceptable but not ideal hand hold or coupling acceptable with another body part: fair: +1
Hand held not acceptable but possible: poor: +2
No handles, awkward, unsafe with any body part: Unacceptable: +3

Step 12: Score B, Find Column in Table C
Add values from steps 10 & 11 to obtain Score B. Find column in Table C and match with Score A in row from step 6 to obtain Table C Score.

Step 13: Activity Score
+1 1 or more body parts are held for longer than 1 minute (static)
+1 Repeated small range actions (more than 4x per minute)
+1 Action causes rapid large range changes in postures or unstable base

Task name: _____ Reviewer: _____ Date: ____/____/____

This tool is provided without warranty. The author has provided this tool as a simple means for applying the concepts provided in REBA.

Figure 4.5.2: Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) employee assessment worksheet

REFERENCES

7. References

1. European Agency for Safety and Health at Work: European risk of observatory report. *OSH in Figures: Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders in the EU — Facts and Figures.*; 2010. doi:10.2802/10952
2. Summers K, Bajorek Z, Bevan S. *Self - Management of Chronic Musculoskeletal Disorders and Employment: The Work Foundation.*; 2014.
3. Luttmann A, Jäger M, Griefahn B, Caffier G, Liebers F, Steinberg U. *Preventing Musculoskeletal Disorders in the Workplace.*; 2003.
http://www.who.int/occupational_health/publications/en/oehmsd3.pdf.
Accessed October 2, 2018.
4. International Labour Office (ILO). *International Labour Organization XIX World Congress on Safety and Health at Work: ILO Introductory Report: Global Trends and Challenges on Occupational Safety and Health.*
http://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/@ed_protect/@protrav/@safework/documents/publication/wcms_162662.pdf. Accessed September 27, 2018.
5. World Health Organization (WHO). *Preventing Disease through Healthy Environments.*; 2016.
http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/204585/9789241565196_eng.pdf?sequence=1. Accessed September 27, 2018.
6. van Vledder N, Louw Q. The effect of a workstation chair and computer screen height adjustment on neck and upper back musculoskeletal pain and sitting comfort in office workers. *South African J Physiother.* 2015;71(1):279.
doi:10.4102/sajp.v71i1.279
7. Khan R, Surti A, Rehman R, Ali U. Knowledge and practices of ergonomics in

- computer users. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 2012;62(3):213-217.
8. Abarghouei NS, Nasab HH. An Ergonomic Evaluation and Intervention Model : Macro ergonomic approach. *Int J Sci Eng Res Vol 3, Issue 2, Febr 2012 ISSN 2229-5518.* 2012;3(IJSER):1-7.
 9. Khattak JK, Khan MA, Haq AU, Arif M, Minhas AA. Occupational stress and burnout in Pakistan ' s banking sector. *African J Bus Manag.* 2011;5(3):810-817. doi:10.5897/AJBM10.395
 10. Naqvi M, Shahid M, Nizami G, Ali S. Practice of Ergonomics among the bankers of Private and Public Sector Banks. *Pakistan J Rehabil.* 2012;1(2):1-7.
 11. McAtamney L, Nigel Corlett E. RULA: a survey method for the investigation of work-related upper limb disorders. *Appl Ergon.* 1993;24(2):91-99.
 12. Levanon Y, Lerman Y, Gefen A, Ratzon NZ. Validity of the modified RULA for computer workers and reliability of one observation compared to six. *Ergonomics.* 2014;57(12):1856-1863. doi:10.1080/00140139.2014.952350
 13. de Wall M, van Riel MP, Snijders CJ, van Wingerden JP. The effect on sitting posture of a desk with a 10 degree inclination for reading and writing. *Ergonomics.* 1991;34(5):575-584. doi:10.1080/00140139108967338
 14. Das B, Sengupta AK. Industrial workstation design: a systematic ergonomics approach. *Appl Ergon.* 1996;27(3):157-163.
 15. Namwongsa S, Puntumetakul R, Neubert MS, Chaiklieng S, Boucaut R. Ergonomic risk assessment of smartphone users using the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) tool. *PLoS One.* 2018;13(8):e0203394. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0203394
 16. Sellschop I V, Myezwa H, Mudzi W, Musenge E. Ergonomic behaviour of learners in a digitally driven school environment: Modification using an

- ergonomic intervention programme. *South African J Physiother.* 2018;74(1):348. doi:10.4102/sajp.v74i1.348
17. Valentim DP, Sato T de O, Comper MLC, Silva AM da, Boas CV, Padula RS. Reliability, Construct Validity and Interpretability of the Brazilian version of the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) and Strain Index (SI). *Brazilian J Phys Ther.* 2018;22(3):198-204. doi:10.1016/j.bjpt.2017.08.003
 18. Dockrell S, O'Grady E, Bennett K, et al. An investigation of the reliability of Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) as a method of assessment of children's computing posture. *Appl Ergon.* 2012;43(3):632-636. doi:10.1016/j.apergo.2011.09.009
 19. Bao S, Howard N, Spielholz P, Silverstein B. Two posture analysis approaches and their application in a modified rapid upper limb assessment evaluation. *Ergonomics.* 2007;50(12):2118-2136. doi:10.1080/00140130701458230
 20. Gandavadi A, Ramsay JRE, Burke FJT. Assessment of dental student posture in two seating conditions using RULA methodology - a pilot study. *Br Dent J.* 2007;203(10):601-605. doi:10.1038/bdj.2007.1047
 21. Breen R, Pyper S, Rusk Y, Dockrell S. An investigation of children's posture and discomfort during computer use. *Ergonomics.* 2007;50(10):1582-1592. doi:10.1080/00140130701584944
 22. Massaccesi M, Pagnotta A, Soccetti A, Masali M, Masiero C, Greco F. Investigation of work-related disorders in truck drivers using RULA method. *Appl Ergon.* 2003;34(4):303-307. doi:10.1016/S0003-6870(03)00052-8
 23. Fountain LJK. Examining the relationship between rapid upper limb assessment's (RULA) postural scoring system and selected physiological and psychophysiological measures. 2000.

http://www.collectionscanada.gc.ca/obj/s4/f2/dsk1/tape4/PQDD_0021/MQ57234.pdf. Accessed September 26, 2018.

24. Indian Council of Medical Research. *National Ethical Guidelines for Biomedical Research Involving Children.*; 2017.
25. World Medical Association. World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki. Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects. *J Am Med Assoc.* 2013;310(20):2191-2194. doi:10.1001/jama.2013.281053
26. Koo TK, Li MY. A Guideline of Selecting and Reporting Intraclass Correlation Coefficients for Reliability Research. *J Chiropr Med.* 2016;15(2):155-163. doi:10.1016/j.jcm.2016.02.012

[Informed Consent form for the computer operators]

This Informed Consent Form is for men and women who are working in bank and using computers during maximum working hours in State Bank of India and who we are inviting to participate in research on Reliability and Validity study. The title of our research project is **"A study to examine the intra reliability of rapid upper limb assessment (RULA) in computer operators."**

Name of Principal Investigator: Ajay Kumar

Name of Organization: Srinivas College of physiotherapy & research center,
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru-1

Name of Proposal: A study to examine the intrarater reliability of rapid upper limb assessment (RULA) in computer operators.

This Informed Consent Form has two parts:

- Information Sheet (to share information about the research with you)
- Certificate of Consent (for signatures if you agree to take part)

You will be given a copy of the full Informed Consent For

PART I: Information Sheet

Introduction

I, Dr. Ajay Kumar, working for the Srinivas College of physiotherapy & research center, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru. We are doing research on establishing the validity and reliability of RULA (rapid upper limb assessment) among the computer. I am going to give you information and invite you to be part of this

research. You do not have to decide today whether or not you will participate in the research. Before you decide, you can talk to anyone you feel comfortable with about the research.

There may be some words that you do not understand. Please ask me to stop as we go through the information and I will take time to explain. If you have questions later, you can ask them of me, the study doctor or the staff.

Purpose of the research

Awkward body posture while typing is associated with musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) among the computer users. RULA (rapid upper limb assessment) is a survey method developed for use in ergonomics investigations of workplaces where work-related upper limb disorders are reported. This tool requires no special equipment in providing a quick assessment of the postures of the neck, trunk and upper limbs along with muscle function and the external loads experienced by the body. A coding system is used to generate an action list which indicates the level of intervention required to reduce the risks of injury due to physical loading on the operator. RULA is a subjective observation method of posture analysis that focuses on the upper body, but includes the lower body. Their applicability to the bank employees is obsolete. Hence there is need to develop and validate the scale to be used among the Indian. The reason we are doing this research is to find out the validity and the intrarater reliability of RULA in computer operators.

Type of Research Intervention

This research will involve a single administration of validated scales of RULA during visits to your working area, State Bank of India, Mangaluru, Karnataka

Participant selection

We are inviting all the bank employee from State Bank of India, Mangaluru, Karnataka using computers during working hours.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary. It is your choice whether to participate or not. Whether you choose to participate or not, all the services you receive from the bank will continue and nothing will change. If you choose not to participate in this research project, you will not be involved in our research, and we will tell you more about it later. You may change your mind later and stop participating even if you agreed earlier.

Information RULA testing phase

The RULA used in this research are in reliability and validity testing phase. There are no known side effects/problems or risks.

Procedures and Protocol

During the research you make two visits to the clinic.

- In the first visit, the employee working with computers will be evaluated with RULA and REBA, standardized criterion measure to establish the concurrent validity. We will also ask you a few questions about your general health and measure how tall you are and how much you weigh.
- At the next visit, which will be within two weeks, you will again be evaluated with the RULA. Then will be asked some questions about your health.

Duration

The research takes place over 2 days in total. During that time, it will be necessary for you to come to the hospital 2 days, for 30 minutes to one hour each day.

Side Effects

As already mentioned, as this will be an assessment scale, no known side effects is associated with RULA, but can have some unwanted effects. It can make you tired during the performance of test. It is possible that it may also cause some problems that we are not aware of. However, we will follow you closely and keep track of any unwanted effects or any problems. We may stop the use of RULA and REBA if you feel uncomfortable.

Risks

By participating in this research it is possible that you will be at greater risk than you would otherwise be. There is, for example, a risk of loss of attention during the working hours due to the video recordings of RULA. While the possibility of this

happening is very low, you should still be aware of the possibility. We will try to decrease the chances of this event occurring, but if something unexpected happens, we will provide you with free treatment.

Benefits

If you participate in this research, you will have the following benefits: any interim illnesses will be treated at concession charge to you. There may not be any benefit for you but your participation is likely to help us find the answer to the research question. There may not be any benefit to the society at this stage of the research, but future generations are likely to benefit.

Reimbursements

You will not be given any other money or gifts to take part in this research

Confidentiality

With this research, something out of the ordinary is being done in your community. It is possible that if others in the community are aware that you are participating, they may ask you questions. We will not be sharing the identity of those participating in the research.

The information that we collect from this research project will be kept confidential. Information about you that will be collected during the research will be put away and

no-one but the researchers will be able to see it. Any information about you will have a number on it instead of your name. Only the researchers will know what your number is and we will lock that information up with a lock and key. It will not be shared with or given to anyone except [name who will have access to the information, such as research sponsors, DSMB board, your clinician, etc].)

Sharing the Results

The knowledge that we get from doing this research will be shared with you through community meetings before it is made widely available to the public. Confidential information will not be shared. There will be small meetings in the community and these will be announced. After these meetings, we will publish the results in order that other interested people may learn from our research.

Right to Refuse or Withdraw

You do not have to take part in this research if you do not wish to do so. You may also stop participating in the research at any time you choose. It is your choice and all of your rights will still be respected.

Alternatives to Participating

If you do not wish to take part in the research, you will be provided with the established standard treatment available at the centre/institute/hospital. People who have knee osteoarthritis are given

Who to Contact

If you have any questions you may ask them now or later, even after the study has started. If you wish to ask questions later, you may contact any of the following: [Dr. Ajay Kumar, Srinivas College of physiotherapy & research center, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru, Karnataka/telephone number/e-mail])

This proposal has been reviewed and approved by Srinivas University Ethics Committee, which is a committee whose task it is to make sure that research participants are protected from harm. It has also been reviewed by the Ethics Review Committee of the World Health Organization (WHO), which is funding/sponsoring/supporting the study.

PART II: Certificate of Consent

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions that I have asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to participate as a participant in this research.

Print Name of Participant _____

Signature of Participant _____

Date _____

Day/month/year

If illiterate

A literate witness must sign (if possible, this person should be selected by the participant and should have no connection to the research team). Participants who are illiterate should include their thumb-print as well.

I have witnessed the accurate reading of the consent form to the potential participant, and the individual has had the opportunity to ask questions. I confirm that the individual has given consent freely.

Print name of witness _____

AND Left Thumb

print of participant

Signature of witness _____

Date _____

Day/month/year

I, Dr. Ajay Kumar have accurately read out the information sheet to the potential participant, and to the best of my ability made sure that the participant understands the details on the information sheet.

I confirm that the participant was given an opportunity to ask questions about the study, and all the questions asked by the participant have been answered correctly and to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

A copy of this Informed Consent Form (ICF) has been provided to the participant.

Print Name of Researcher/person taking the consent: Dr. Ajay Kumar, MPT

**Signature of Researcher /person taking the
consent** _____

Date _____

Day/month/year